

Child Trafficking and Sale of Children

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Introduction

In my paper I would like to say some words what I learnt and known about trafficking and sale of children in Tamilnadu and also India. Trafficking of children is a form of human trafficking and defined as the recruitment transportation, transfer, harboring, and of a child purpose of slavery forced labour and sex exploitation.

Children trafficking and modern slavery are child abuse, children are recruitment moved or transported and then exploitation, forced to work or sold child sexual exploitation. In male children are making beggars to beg in the streets in developed town streets. Female children are sold for sexual exploitation. So we are be careful for the child trafficking and sale of children.

Types of Child Trafficking

I like to the types of child trafficking by the traffickers and sale of children

- Forced to labour
- Sexual exploitation
- Children in armed forces
- Children in drug trades
- Child begging
- Adoption
- Sale of children
- Demographic

Children Armed Forces

A child associated with an armed force or refers to any person below 18 years of age who is, or who has been, recruited or used by an armed force or armed group in any capacity, including but not limited to children, boys and girls, used as fighters, cooks, porters, spies or for sexual purposes. A trafficking child has sent to armed groups to do such works including sexual exploitation

Child Begging

The main cause for begging using children is the widespread poverty among our families. ... Based on the findings, it could be

argued and maintained that the main causes of begging phenomenon involving children as guides were poverty, lack of education, sympathy attraction, lack of proper orientation and laziness

Solutions for Reducing Child Trafficking

1. To paste the Foster the spread of education for anti trafficking,
2. To give awareness among parents and communities,
3. To keep Strict laws in place to prevent child trafficking.
4. To Encouraging business to not use child labour.
5. To give awarence education to children through the school education,
6. To understand and hear the children feeling and emotions
7. To give practice solve the problems of adults

Sale of children

The sale children is related issue for chid trafficking .A male or female child trafficking to sale for sexual exploitation.The Optional Protocol on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography is a protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child and requires parties to prohibit the sale of children, child prostitution and child pornography.

The main purpose of sale of children to slaves for house hold works,and brothels or in the homes of families out of poverty and desperation.

The poor parents also volantery to sale their children for money .Most of the countries population suffers from poverty. Due to poverty parents cannot afford the studies of their children and make them earn their wages from a tender age in fact,they we well aware of the grief of losing their loved ones to poverty many times

Forced begging involved both boys and girls. The research points towards poverty as a key cause of forced child begging and the wider problem of begging in all of the settings examined. Poverty and its consequences and causes, such as migration and discrimination, are often the root cause of forced child begging.

Adoptation

Children may be trafficked for the purposes of adoption, particularly international adoption. Children are sourced from orphanages or kidnapped, or parents may be tricked. In india there are lot of illegal adaptation to trafficking children for foreign countries. The poor parents willing to sale their children for money and other demands ot their own life to illegal adaptation.

Solutions of Trafficking and Sale of Children

- To make voluntary group like lions,Rotary,social welfare groups to avoid the problems in to meetings held on annually.
- To make a special team for anti-trafficking and contact school seminars and awareness programmes also.
- To spread the advertisement to keep their children their parents attention.
- To instruction for school administration to keep the students in proper attention with regular attention.
- To check the school management and headmaster whether the students reach the house safely.
- To make sure if the students go or come their parents or not.
- To protect the Adult children in school campus,and also give suggestions to their parents keep their safe in house and surroundings.

- To contact proper meetings for child abuse, trafficking and sale of the children in school for blocklevel and district levels.
- To arranged district level team,with a police higher official for child abuse,trafficking and sale of the children.
- To give the awarenessmessage through the social medias like facebook, whatsapp, twitter also...

Conclusion

Child trafficking is a fast growing network and has to be stopped. Government has to work with the help of NGO's to develop, evaluate and implement laws and provisions to stop the crime. The exploiters have to be punished rather than the exploited. Creating awareness and educating people is important. We need to stop supporting the act by refraining from giving donation to the beggars on the street as helping them encourages the crime even more. The society and government needs to focus on Prevention, Prosecution and Protection. The government should adopt proper measures to prevent severe kind of child trafficking. Awareness in the society has to be created by educating and informing people and the victims of child trafficking about the causes and effects of the different forms of child trafficking. The government needs to redefine laws and make sure the laws are implemented efficiently. Government needs to make continuous efforts with the help of NGOs and society to abolish all forms of child trafficking. Serious action needs to be taken against the trafficking chain and everyone involved in the crime must be punished by law. We must teach about child abuse and trafficking among the students in the classroom. In the school campus we must add for CCTV previllage to watch the students activities and also outsiders activities...